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COMPETITIVENESS FACTORS IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *The paper describes importance and factors of competitiveness of the country in the economy of the world. As well as, it analyzes key advantages of Uzbekistan to reach competitive market goals.*

Key words: *competitiveness, economy of the country, natural resources, state regulation*

The role and rank of the country's economy in the world economy are determined by its level of competitiveness. International Economic Competition is the most important factor in technical development and management of technologies are constantly updated under its influence.

The theory of regional competitiveness is new approach on its content, as a concept it is forming and discovering new meanings. There are different views and definitions on it. In our opinion, competitiveness of the region is to use effective from its competitive advantages, to produce of competitive goods and services and at the end to increase the living standards of the population.

International experience and research show that the competitiveness of the region is in many respects its natural-economic determined by the presence and degree of potential. Potential evaluation-based approach clearly outlines the region's competitive advantages. Region's key potentials that effect the level of competitiveness are natural resource potential, human factor, financial, environmental and institutional developments.

In many respects, regional competitiveness depends on natural resources, development of the region, the effectiveness of state regulation, as well as the effective use of innovative projects.

Uzbekistan is a country that the economy is developing steadily with high pictures, standard of living of population is growing steadily and the position of the country in the world markets is further strengthened. All of the implementation

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of market reforms in Uzbekistan is to increase internal and external competitiveness in the economy.

Uzbekistan has the following comparative advantages in the world economy:

- Availability of favorable natural and climatic conditions for agricultural development;

- Possession of rich natural resources and recreational resources;

- Development of tourism with a rich cultural and historical heritage allows;

- Favorable geographical location of the country;

- Diligence and entrepreneurship of the population of Uzbekistan

- Availability of capable labor resources.

Analyzing the competitive advantages of Uzbekistan the following can be distinguished:

- Stability of the political and legal system of the country;

- Human development (education, health, social needs) large investments;

Average length of life of the population;

- Competitiveness of labor resources;

- High level of education of the population.

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